

INCLUSIVE CREATION OF PUBLIC POLICIES THROUGH THE REGULATORY MECHANISMS

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Abstract:

The civic participation in the process of creation of the public policies should improve the quality of democracy and give it its epistemological value. The public policy can be inclusive if its creation involves, on the basis of equality, all citizens who have their interests in conflict and can be affected by it. The paper will examine the civic participation in the process of creation of the laws through Regulatory Impact Assessment (RIA) tool in the Republic of Macedonia. Although the legal framework establishes the modes for obligatory civic participation, most of the laws are brought without substantial debate and without meaningful involvement of the affected groups.

Key words: *Regulatory Impact Assessment, civic participation, public policies, democracy*

1. Introduction

The involvement and participation of the citizens in the decision-making process, the transparency and accountability are the foundation of democracy. The civic participation in the process of creation of the public policies should improve the quality of democracy and give it its epistemological value. The public policy can be inclusive if its creation involves, on the basis of equality, all citizens who have their interests in conflict and are affected by it. This should guarantee greater control over the public authorities and should ascertain an opportunity to hear the voices of those who are underrepresented in the political processes (Santiago Nino, 1996).

This paper focuses on the civic participation in the process of creation of the public policies through Regulatory Impact Assessment (RIA) tool (as a standard mode for creating a “good regulation”) – seen as well as a mode for creating inclusive public policies. It presents the concept of RIA and how its essence can support the core ideas of the deliberative democracy. In particular, the focus is on the practical implementation of RIA in the Republic of Macedonia and its inclusiveness seen through civic involvement in the procedures. The paper argues that although the legal framework establishes the modes for obligatory civic participation through RIA mechanism, most of the laws are brought without substantial debate, without the meaningful involvement of the affected groups, without taking into account the citizens views i.e. they don't affect the brought decisions. Although RIA is an excessive tool that should ensure the creation of inclusive, evidence-based policies, the way in which it is performed does not reach the objectives

and shows a significant gap between the theory and the practice, between the accepted legal frame and its actual implementation.

2. Theoretical framework

There is no widely accepted definition of democracy. In general, we can say that democracy is a form of governance that protects the citizen freedoms and ensures a maintenance of a minimum public good necessary for the implementation of the social objectives. The democracy enables each individual (directly or through elected representatives) to participate in the creation of a decision from which she/he is directly concern. The will of the majority should prevail – is a notion that has secondary importance in the contemporary theory concerning the democracy. From that point, the idea of democracy is not simply an idea of the majority rule, but a reflection that every person, whether a minority or majority, have basic rights, including the right to participate in the public life (Crawford, 2000).

The right to political participation is guaranteed through major human rights instruments. Nonetheless, it is argued that the traditional institutes for the democratic decision making are less successful in involving the citizens in the political processes (Fishkin 1991; Dryzek 1990). In that regard, the idea of “deliberative democracy” (occurred at the beginning of the 80s.) focuses on the improvements of nature and the form of the civic involvement in the policy-making process. The deliberative democracy is a modern form of social establishment that stimulates civil efficiency, generates care for the collective problems and encourages aware citizenship - capable to act for the public good (Cronin, 1999). The democratic legitimacy derives from the free, public and rational discussion carried out among competent citizens that mutually agree in the context of openness and equality thought recognized channels of communication (Habermas, 2007). The theoreticians that favor deliberative democracy praise the intellectual debate, the public use of the ratio and neutrality, the impartial quest for truth (Held, 2008).

Therefore, the social deliberation is a manner through which the inclusive policies are achieved. The public policies are inclusive only if the democratic process of their creation is a product of rules which provide, to the maximum extent possible, the involvement in the discussion those who are directly concerned by the discussion; freedom of the participants to express themselves; equal opportunities under which the participation and involvement is carried out; justification of the proposals; the morality of the debate instead of pure presentation of the interests (Santiago Nino, 1996). Among the others, the goal of the deliberative democracy is to improve the process through which the citizens will influence the decision makers and in the same time to improve the mechanisms through which the politicians will be informed about the standpoints and priorities of the citizens. From that point, the citizens must be informed, consulted and actively involved. This leads towards better public policies, greater trust in the institutions and stronger democracy (Cronin, 1999). The process is efficient if it is accompanied by democratic public culture and representative institutions; relevant civic education and awareness; pluralism of values – taking into consideration the opinions and facts; putting own views into critical relation with the views of others, defining and defending the own priorities (Santiago Nino, 1996).

3. Regulatory Impact Assessment (RIA) tool as a standard regulatory mechanism

Having on mind the above - mentioned ideas it is needless to say that the increased complexity of modern governance requires a systematic approach towards a policy-making process that should be inclusive and evidence-based. Operative and well-focused regulation brought in a transparent manner are increasing competition, protecting the citizens and leads to the more functional market economy. Poorly designed regulation generates unnecessary burdens to the ones affected by it, can create obstacles to efficient markets and leads to unfair wealth distribution (Regulating Better, 2004). In that respect, the participation of the citizens in the policymaking process should be ensured through various modes (working groups, workshops, seminars, conferences, public hearings, reception days, roundtables, advisory bodies, etc.) and should be effective and quality driven. Civic participation should be guaranteed in all the phases of the process i.e. identification of the problem, development of the policies, decision making, implementation, and evaluation.

There is no unique model concerning regulatory management that is the best one and applicable to all. Thus in that regard - each country has a different approach. However, EU adopted a policy on Better Regulation and recommended RIA as a core instrument. Thus, RIA originally set as an OCDE economic tool for estimation of the cost and the benefits from the proposed regulation became an integral part of representative democracy. As a result, many countries adopted RIA to ensure that their policy decisions are based on the qualitative and quantitative information. In that respect, RIA assists the policy-makers in the design, implementation, monitoring and, improvements of the public policies (OECD, 2010). As a summary RIA ensures that the adopted proposal best meets the Government's objectives and social expectations at the same time. To reach that goal, except the economic analysis, RIA presumes efficient consultations with all interested stakeholders to plan the implementation and enforcement of the new and amended regulation ensuring maximization of compliance and diminishing of the costs to citizens, businesses, and the state (Sutcliffe & Court, 2005).

RIA is effective only if the options for resolving the problem, including alternatives to regulation – are considered; the evidence-based analysis of the risks, costs, and benefits of the options are undertaken; the effective consultation with all interested stakeholders are performed; the implementation and enforcement of the policies and laws are carefully planned (Agca & Shikova, 2016). Since public opinion is a critical component of the process, RIA tends to increase the civic participation, civic mobilization and action, widening the scope for possible inclusions, and in the same time strengthening the accountability and transparency in regulatory actions (Kirkpatrick & Parker, 2007). If applied properly the activities allied should result in better public policy, greater trust in the government/institutions and a stronger democracy.

4. Practical implementation/ shortcomings in the civic participation

On the regulatory level, the OECD and EU actively promote the use of RIA as part of a wider regulatory reform strategy and provide advice and review its implementation progress. On EU level, in 2009 the Competitiveness Council underlined that all EU institutions and the Member States should put Better Regulation principles at the heart of their decision-making processes. In

that sense, over the last 10 years, many countries have adopted policies focusing on the improvement of the quality of the regulations and the governance.

Table 1: No. of jurisdictions that are implementing RIA

Source: 2014 Regulatory Indicators Survey results, Measuring Regulatory Performance

As for the EU candidate countries, the new EU enlargement standards, the Copenhagen criteria, require stability of the institutions that guarantee democracy; rule of law; democratic governance; human rights and functional market economy. The countries that strive for economic development and prosperity of the society should introduce RIA into their legislative systems in order to improve policy making, quality of legislation, enhance transparency, citizen’s participation and rule of law.

Following those guidelines, as EU candidate country, the Republic of Macedonia has shown a strong commitment to becoming part of the EU and started the process of harmonization of the domestic legislation with the *Acquis Communautaire*. As a part of it, RIA was formally introduced into the domestic legislation 2009 and it is obligatory for all legislative proposals except the ones brought by the urgent procedure, the Budget and the laws for execution of the Budget. The legal framework for RIA comprises Methodology; Rules of procedures and Decisions about the format and content of the RIA forms. The Methodology predicts an obligation to involve stakeholders (business community, citizen’s groups etc..) from the very beginning of the regulatory process and strives for public participation through its every stage. The civic participation should be undertaken by the electronic means (informing the citizens, gathering opinions and suggestions), as well as through direct participatory forms such as focus group discussions, public arguments, and workshops. All the laws need to be accessible through the Unique National Electronic Register (ENER) where the citizens can freely access all the relevant information about the decision-making processes, share their opinion and comments and assess the proposed laws at different stages.

According to the accepted standards, the “good consultation process”, that comprises civic involvement, should be effective, timely and should ensure quality. The opinions need to be considered and the results and the effects achieved should be systematized and published. The process needs to be done at every stage of RIA based on a clear description of the draft regulation and should result in the adoption of the best practices envisaged in the brought laws.

However, in practice, the quality of the undertaken RIA analysis for estimating the cost and the benefits of the proposed or amendment regulative is not sufficient and in most of the cases, the consultations are not properly done. In the policy creation process, the concerned stakeholders are not fully involved, such as the civil society organizations and the business community. The involvement is only sectorial, exclusive and no feedback is provided. In that sense, there is a lack of meaningful participation of the citizens in the decision making process and lack of a systematic and coherent approach. As a result, the most of the adopted policies are “extinguishing the fire” and are responses to crises. The measures are populist, brought in a situation of an inter-ministerial and inter-ministerial rivalry, under the strong political influence. Consequently, many adopted laws are fundamentally changed many times because of unpredicted problems that are occurring during their implementation period. This situation can be overcome with a substantial consultation process and external quality controls during the preparation of laws, whose creation is limited to the use of *ad hoc* experts and without meaningful and substantial public involvement. All of that shows a clear misbalance between the theory and the practice in the implementation of the RIA in the Republic of Macedonia (Shikova, 2017).

The possible reasons can be found in past legacies and general slowness of public administration reforms, the lack of capacities and incentives, or low level of political/administrative culture that not support the citizen-oriented approach that is in the essence of the creation of the inclusive policies. Nonetheless, the situation is not much different in EU countries with stronger democratic traditions and regulatory mechanisms in place that took measures to implement RIA. Although most OECD and EU countries had systematically adopted stakeholder engagement practices, yet their practical involvement is often late in the process.

Table 2: *Involvement of the stakeholders in the process*

5. Conclusion

There is an accumulation of both theoretical and empirical work demonstrating that public policies, and the elements in their designs, have important effects on citizenship, justice, and discourse. In that sense traditionally - policy analysis served democracy. In order the democratic processes and institutions to be built around “reasonable” political judgment, several studies are pointing that the civic participation should have a high importance (Bohman & Rehg, 1997) regardless that the attitudes of the citizens are informative in nature and not decisive. Consequently, their opinions need to be taken into account and that is an only way how the inclusive policies can be created. However, despite the efforts and attempts of the governments to alleviate gender, racial, and ethnic bias and unequal treatment with introducing regulatory mechanisms (such as RIA) that should enable greater civic participation in policy creation process and make it more inclusive - disparities remain. The gap between the ideas and the practical realization is evident both in non EU, in EU and OCDE developed countries. Although there is rhetoric aimed towards greater involvement of the citizens in policy creation, the process remains unfairly unequal and non-sufficiently inclusive irrespectively the sophisticated regulatory tools (Šikova, 2017).

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